

Speeding up the Iron Losses Calculation using Clustering Technics

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The Finite Element method is widely used to study and design electromagnetic devices. This method is very accurate but often requires huge computational time even during the post processing step where quantities of interest are calculated. In this article, we propose to apply and to compare clustering methods, i.e. the K-Means and Gaussian Mixture methods, in order to reduce the computational time of the iron loss distribution in a postprocessing stage. Indeed, the iron loss distribution calculation relies only on the calculation on only a few elements of mesh and not on all elements like in the case of the standard method. The proposed methods are tested on a nonlinear magnetic example based on an axial flux machine showing a good agreement between the iron losses distribution obtained by the standard and the proposed methods.

Index Terms—Finite Element Model, Iron Losses calculation, Clustering methods

I. INTRODUCTION

FINITE ELEMENT (FE) models are widely used now for the design and the study of electromagnetic devices. Such models lead to virtual prototypes representing very accurately the behavior of the real device. However, these kinds of models are very time-consuming. This is the reason why a lot of research is ongoing on model order reduction technic in order to speed up the solving of the FE models [1,2]. However, the post processing step once the FE model has been solved can be also time consuming especially when a local quantity should be calculated on numerous nodes or elements of the mesh. An alternative consists in using technics in order to select some specific nodes or elements on which the local quantity is calculated and then to extrapolate on entities of the mesh. Recently, in [3], a method based on Energy Conserving Sampling and Weighting method has been proposed in order to calculate the force by only calculating local forces on specific points.

In this paper, we propose to apply two clustering methods, the K-Mean method [4-6] and the Gaussian Mixture method [5, 7], in order to speed up the calculation of the iron losses distribution. The two clustering methods are first described. The second part presents the iron loss calculation approach. The application of clustering methods to reduce computational time is detailed. Finally, the efficiency of the two methods in terms of accuracy and computation time are evaluated and compared

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to the standard approach on an axial flux permanent magnet machine.

II. CLUSTERING METHODS

A. K-means method

We consider a dataset holding N data points. In the following, the data points x_n are $M \times 1$ real valued vectors. The algorithm aims to partition the dataset into K clusters defined by a point m_k , so-called centroid. A data point x_n belongs to only one cluster k such that its distance with the centroid m_k is the shortest among all the K clusters. In our case, to measure the distance, the Euclidean norm is used. The centroids are not known a priori and can be determined by the iterative algorithm presented in Fig. 1. At the end of the iterative process, the centroids m_k doesn't correspond exactly to a data point so we choose as new centroid of the cluster k , the closest data point x_n of the cluster K to m_k .

B. Gaussian Mixture method

In the K-means method a point x_n belongs only to one cluster. In the Gaussian Mixture (GM) method, the approach is not deterministic anymore but probabilistic. We evaluate here the likelihood of belonging of a data point x_n to a cluster k . This likelihood is evaluated by a scalar y_{nk} belonging to $[0,1]$. If y_{nk} is close to 1, the data point x_n probably belongs to the cluster k . In this probabilistic approach, each cluster is associated with a Gaussian law $N(x, \mu_k, \Sigma_k)$ with μ_k the mean and Σ_k the variance. The scalars y_{nk} and the parameters μ_k and Σ_k are obtained by applying the algorithm presented in Fig.2. Like in the k-means method, at the end of the iterative process, the means μ_k doesn't correspond exactly to a data point so we choose as new centroid of the cluster k , the closest data point to μ_k . In the K-means method, a data point belongs to only one cluster. In the Gaussian Mixture method, a data point x_n belongs to all the clusters with a probability of y_{nk} for the cluster k .

Fig. 1: Iterative algorithm to determine the centroids m_k and clusters by the K-means method.

Fig. 2: Iterative algorithm to determine the scalars y_{nk} associated to each data point x_n and cluster k .

III. IRON LOSS CALCULATION METHOD

Let's consider a device modeled by the FE method in the time domain. We are interested in calculating the iron loss distribution in a ferromagnetic region. A standard method consists in determining the time evolution of the magnetic flux density $B_e(t)$ on each element e of the mesh by solving the FE model in the time domain considering a non-linear but univoc behavior of the ferromagnetic materials. Then, in a post processing step, from $B_e(t)$ on a period, the iron loss densities

p_e are determined in each element e of the ferromagnetic region [8]. The iron losses on the element e are given by:

$$P_e = p_e V_e \rho \quad (1)$$

With V_e the volume of the element e and ρ the volume density of the ferromagnetic material. If we denote by E the number of elements in the ferromagnetic region, the total iron losses P_{tot} is given by:

$$P_{tot} = \sum_{e=1}^E P_e \quad (2)$$

If the ferromagnetic region contains a large number E of elements, the computational time for the post processing step can be significant. However, in practice, it appears that in numerous elements, the term $B_e(t)$ is quite similar leading to almost equivalent iron loss density values. The idea is then to determine a small number K of elements on which the iron loss density p_e is calculated and then from these densities to express the iron loss density on all other elements. In order to do that, we propose to apply the two clustering methods presented in section II combined with some snapshots of iron loss density distributions obtained from different precalculated operating points. In the following, we denote by M the number of operating points and \mathbf{p}_e the vector $M \times 1$ containing the iron loss density on the element e corresponding to the M operating points. These vectors \mathbf{p}_e are the data points (denoted x_n is section II) on which the clustering methods will be applied. The centroids are the elements e_k with $k \in [1, K]$. The list $L = (e_1, \dots, e_K)$ contains the index of the elements, centroids of the K clusters.

A. K-means method

By applying the k-means method (see algorithm in Fig.1) on the data set composed of E vectors \mathbf{p}_e , we can extract K clusters gathering elements with similar iron losses for the M operating points and also K elements e_k corresponding to the centroids of the K clusters. Once the clusters and centroids are determined, the iron loss densities p_e as well as the total iron losses P_{tot} can be calculated, in post processing step for any new operating point, by assuming that the iron loss density is constant for all element belonging to the same cluster and equal to the iron loss density determined on the centroids e_k with $k \in [1, K]$. Once the simulation of an operating point is carried out using the FE method, the iron loss densities are calculated on the K elements e_k . Then, the iron loss density on an element e is calculated by assuming that the density p_e^{KM} is equal to p_{e_k} with k the index of the cluster the element e belongs to. The iron loss P_e^{KM} on the element e is then given by (see (1)):

$$P_e^{KM} = p_{e_k} V_e \rho \quad (3)$$

The number of iron loss calculations from $B_e(t)$ is done on only K elements. The total iron losses P_{tot}^{KM} are obtained using (2).

B. Gaussian Mixture method

By applying the Gaussian Mixture method on the data set composed of the E vectors \mathbf{p}_e , the elements e_k centroids of the clusters can be determined as well as the scalars y_{nk} . Once the FE simulation is carried out, the iron loss distribution as well as the total loss can be calculated in a post processing step following the same idea proposed previously with the K-means

method. First, the iron loss densities p_{e_k} are calculated on the K elements e_k . Then, the iron loss density p_e^{GM} on the element e is given by:

$$p_e^{GM} = \sum_{k=1}^K y_{ek} p_{e_k} \quad (4)$$

Then the iron losses P_e^{GM} on the element e and the total iron losses are given by (1) and (2) respectively by replacing p_e by p_e^{GM} given (4).

In the following, we propose to compare the two methods proposed previously in terms of accuracy and computational time to the brute force approach consisting in calculating the iron losses on each element, this approach being our reference.

IV. APPLICATION

A. Studied electrical machine

We consider in the following an axial flux machine composed of two stators and one rotor. In Fig.3, full and partial views of the geometry of the studied machine with 18 teeth and 12 permanent magnets on the rotor are given. The $B(H)$ curve of ferromagnetic core of the stator is assumed to have a nonlinear behavior (see Fig.4). The iron loss density p in the ferromagnetic material is given by the following expression [8]:

$$p = k_h f \left[\left(\frac{\Delta B_{\perp}}{2} \right)^{\alpha} + \left(\frac{\Delta B_{\parallel}}{2} \right)^{\alpha} \right] + \frac{k_{cl}}{2\pi^2 T} \int_0^T \left[\left(\frac{dB_{\perp}(t)}{dt} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dB_{\parallel}(t)}{dt} \right)^2 \right] dt + \frac{k_{exc}}{8.76 T} \int_0^T \left[\left(\frac{dB_{\perp}(t)}{dt} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dB_{\parallel}(t)}{dt} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{4}} dt \quad (5)$$

With k_h and α coefficients associated with the hysteresis losses, k_{cl} a coefficient associated with the classical losses due to eddy current and k_{exc} a coefficient associated with the excess losses. The terms $B_{\perp}(t)$ and $B_{\parallel}(t)$ represent the evolution along the minor and major axes of the magnetic flux density respectively. The terms ΔB_{\perp} and ΔB_{\parallel} are the peak-to-peak values of the magnetic flux density along the minor and the major axes. Due to the symmetry of the machine (see Fig.3) only a sixth of the geometry is studied. The mesh is made up 210,000 elements in order to be able to calculate accurately the iron losses distribution. The eddy currents in the permanent magnets and in the windings are neglected. According to these assumptions, a magnetostatic model accounting for the rotor movement has been used to simulate the machine. We have considered 361 operating points to cover the whole torque/speed operating range of the machine, which are given in Fig.5.

For each point, we have simulated one period of the machine using the FE software code_Carmel [9]. From the time evolution of the magnetic flux density $B_c(t)$ on each element, we have determined from (5) the iron loss density p_e on each element e and then the total iron losses P_{tot} using (2) The total iron losses P_{tot} has been calculated for each operating point (see Fig.5). In Fig.6, the P_{tot} map in the torque/speed plan is given. We can see that the iron losses are maximum at high speed and decrease when the torque increases, due to the stator flux-weakening by acting on current phase.

Fig.3: Views of the geometry of the studied machine.

Fig.4: $B(H)$ curve of the ferromagnetic material.

Fig.5: Considered operating points of the machine plotted in normalized torque/speed plan.

Fig.6: Normalized total iron losses P_{tot} calculated for the different operating points.

B. Methodology

We want to reconstruct the iron loss map (see Fig. 6) by applying the K-means and Gaussian Mixture methods. These methods have two input parameters, which are the size M of the

dataset and the number K of clusters. To evaluate the influence of M , we have considered three dataset sizes $M=4, 9$ and 16 . The distributions of the data points for each dataset in the torque/speed plan are given in Fig. 7. These datasets have been used as inputs to construct the K clusters and centroids by applying the algorithms presented in Fig.1 and Fig.2. These clusters are then used to calculate the total iron losses P_{tot} of the 361 operating points (see Fig.5) using methods presented in section III.A for the K-means method and III.B for the Gaussian Mixture method. An iron loss map can be then determined and compared to the reference one given in Fig.6.

Fig.7: The three datasets with different sizes $M=4,9,16$ represented in the torque/speed plan. The red circles represent the data points of the data set.

C. One operating point

Before considering the iron loss map, we will focus on one operating point to illustrate the approach. We have applied the two clustering methods with a dataset size $M=9$ and a cluster number $K=6$. The cluster distributions are given in Fig.8. We can see that the two clustering methods lead to different clusters mainly around the tooth tips. However, the elements in the stator core and in the tooth tops belong in both cases to the same cluster. The iron losses distributions calculated with the reference method and with (2) from K-means clusters are given in Fig.9 for an operating point corresponding to a rotation frequency of 0.5 p.u. and a torque of 0.35 p.u. In Fig. 10, we give the distribution of the errors between the iron losses calculated using the reference method and a clustering method. We can see that the error distribution is not the same for the two clustering methods, which was expected since the cluster distribution is not the same. Moreover, with the K-means method, except for a few elements located at the tooth tips where the error is close to 30%, the error remains more homogenous (about 10%) than the error obtained with the Gaussian Mixture.

Fig.8: Cluster distributions obtained with K-means (Top) and Gaussian Mixture (Bottom) methods for $M=9$ and $K=6$.

Fig.9: Iron loss distribution calculated using the reference method for rotation frequency of 0.5 p.u. and a torque of 0.35 p.u.

Fig.10: Distribution of the error between the iron losses calculated using the reference method and a clustering method (K-means (top) and Gaussian Mixture (Bottom)) with $M=9$ and $K=5$.

D. Iron loss map

We have applied the approach presented in the previous section in order to calculate for each operating point the total iron losses P_{tot} . The iron loss distributions are different from an operating point to another due to magnetic saturation and the flux weakening control. These differences arise mainly at the

tooth tips. The iron loss maps constructed by applying the K-means and Gaussian Mixture methods with $M=9$ and $K=6$ are presented in Fig.11 and in Fig.12 respectively. The two maps are similar to the reference map (see Fig.6). Error maps corresponding to the difference in percentage between the iron losses calculating by the clustering methods and the reference are presented in Fig.11 and Fig.12. We can see that the error on the total iron losses remains lower than 10,5% for the K-means method and lower than 16% for the Gaussian Mixture method. It appears also that the dataset size doesn't have necessarily to be large because we need only $M=9$ operating points to reconstruct 361 operating points. Moreover, the number of clusters also doesn't need to be high, confirming that the assumption saying that a lot of elements have similar iron loss density evolutions on the whole operating range is correct. In Fig. 13 and Fig.14, the error maps have been presented when $M=16$ and $K=10$, we can see that we can reach an error lower than 5.8% for the K-means method and 8,2% for the Gaussian mixture method, which can be considered acceptable.

To compare in terms of accuracy the two clustering methods versus the reference method, global errors ϵ_{KM} and ϵ_{GM} have been calculated for different values of M and K :

$$\epsilon_{KM} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{361} (P_{tot,i}^{KM} - P_{tot,i}^{ref})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{361} P_{tot,i}^{ref}^2} \quad (6.a)$$

$$\epsilon_{GM} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{361} (P_{tot,i}^{GM} - P_{tot,i}^{ref})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{361} P_{tot,i}^{ref}^2} \quad (6.b)$$

With $P_{tot,i}^{KM}$, $P_{tot,i}^{GM}$ and $P_{tot,i}^{ref}$ the total iron losses for the i^{th} operating point obtained with the K-means, the Gaussian Mixture and the reference methods respectively. Fig.15 and Fig.16 present the global errors in function of the size M of the dataset and the number K of clusters. It appears that globally the K-means method seems to be more accurate in general. However, the global error is not necessarily a decreasing function of M and K . Indeed, for the Gaussian Mixture method, for a fixed value of K , the error is not a decreasing function of M . Moreover, for the K-means method and the Gaussian method, the error is not a decreasing function of the number K of clusters for a fixed value of M . Then, the determination of optimal values for M and K is not straightforward. However, we can see that increasing M and K tends to improve accuracy.

E. Computational time

In Table 1, for the K-means and the Gaussian Mixture methods, we give the computational time required to calculate $K=6$ or 12 clusters from a dataset of size $M=9$ or 16 respectively. It appears that the calculation of clusters is very fast, especially for the K-means methods. By comparing the two algorithms (see Fig.1 and Fig. 2), the Gaussian Mixture requires more time since the number of quantities to determine x_k, μ_k, Σ_k is much higher as well as the number of parameters with the scalars y_{nk} .

TABLE I COMPUTATIONAL TIME TO CALCULATE THE CLUSTERS		
	K-means	Gaussian Mixture
K=6 M=9	0.09 s	2 s
K=12 M=16	0.18 s	6s

Fig.11: Normalized iron loss map calculated by using the K-means method (top) with $M=9$ and $K=6$ and the error map versus the iron loss map (bottom) obtained by calculating the iron losses on each element (Fig.6).

Fig.12: Normalized iron loss map calculated by using the Gaussian Mixture method (Top) with $M=9$ and $K=6$ and the error map (bottom) versus the iron loss map obtained by calculating the iron losses on each element (Fig.6).

Once, the cluster distribution is known. For each new operating point, the calculation of the total iron loss P_{tot} is very fast, especially in the case of the K-means method. Indeed, according to (3), we have:

$$P_{tot}^{KM} = \sum_{k=1}^K P_{e_k} V_k^{KM} \rho \quad (7)$$

With V_k^{KM} the volume of the cluster k which can be precalculated. The time computation is then equal to 10 μ s compared to 1s required for the standard method. With the Gaussian Mixture, the weighted average (4) has to be calculated on each element of the mesh whereas with the K-means method the iron loss density is taken equal to the one of the centroids of the cluster the element belongs to. So, the K-means method is slightly faster than the Gaussian Mixture.

Fig.13: Error map obtained with the K-means method with M=16 and K=12.

Fig.14: Error map obtained with the Gaussian Mixture method with M=16 and K=12.

Fig.15: Global error ϵ_{KM} on the iron loss map calculated by the K-means method for different size M of the dataset and different number K of clusters.

V. CONCLUSION

We have proposed to apply and compare two clustering methods, K-means and Gaussian Mixture methods, in order to reduce the calculation time of the iron losses distribution. The methods have been compared on an axial flux machine. It appears on this application that the K-means leads to slightly more accurate results and enables to reduce drastically the computation time compared to the standard method. In future work, we plan to develop an adaptive procedure to calculate

automatically the size M of the dataset and the number K of clusters.

Fig.16: Global error ϵ_{GM} on the iron loss map calculated by the Gaussian Mixture method for different sizes M of the dataset and different number K of clusters.

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